

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN* Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Secondary selection in rice

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It is generally believed that further selection cannot improve the yield of varieties of self-pollinated crops such as rice that are established by single-plant selection. Even though plants might look uniform in morphological characters, physiologic and economic characters such as yield are believed to deteriorate with further selection because of such factors as progressive accumulation of spontaneous mutations in the polygenes that control yield components, expression of hidden genetic heterogeneity, natural hybridization with other uneconomic genotypes, seed mixture with low yielding varieties, accumulation of external influences that modify the genes, and retention of unsuspected genotypes within selected pure lines.

Secondary selection was followed in three high yielding varieties commonly grown in the Punjab—IR8, Jaya, and Palman 579—to check the sources of deterioration, to exploit useful mutations in the polygenes, and to improve their yields. The procedure involved selection of from 1,500 to 2,000 true-to-type single plants from transplanted crops of each variety, growing progeny of the 100 best plants, testing promising and genetically pure progeny in replicated yield trials, and multiplying the seed of the best strains to replace the old stocks.

The secondary selections of the varieties developed in the first selection cycle (1968–1974) outyielded the bulk varieties by a highly significant margin (see table). That indicates that the yield of bulk stocks might be improved by as much as 23% in IR8, 7.5% in Jaya, and 12.8% in Palman 579. Secondary selection is being continued to improve the yield potential of those and other

Performance of secondary selections of high yielding rice varieties of the Punjab, 1974 yield trials.

Secondary selection (no.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over bulk variety (t/ha)	(%)
<i>IR8</i>			
94	7.4**	0.8	11.5
95	7.9**	1.3	19.3
99	8.2**	1.5	23.7
	6.6	—	—
<i>Jaya</i>			
98	8.05**	0.6	7.5
Bulk	7.4	—	—
<i>Palman 579</i>			
1	5.2**	0.5	11.0
93	5.0**	0.3	6.7
99	5.3**	0.6	12.8
Bulk	4.7	—	—

^a** = highly significant (0.01 level).

LSD 0.05 = 0.172 t/ha; LSD 0.01 = 0.232 t/ha

recently released varieties and to produce breeders' seed of high genetic purity that will serve as the nucleus for foundation and certified seeds to be multiplied yearly. ¶

Rice in Andaman and Nicobar Islands—problems and prospects

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Andaman and Nicobar Islands in the Bay of Bengal are the most isolated parts of the Indian Union. The total area of the two groups of islands is 8,293 sq km; the Andamans account for about 76% of the land area. The climate of the islands is tropical, with only 3 to 5°C annual variation in temperature. Annual rainfall is about 3,000 mm. Humidity is about 80% throughout the year. Rain comes from both southwest and northeast monsoons. The dry season, from January